

TYPES OF PREPARATION OF HEAVY ATHLETES

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Abstract: In this thesis, there is enough thought about how weightlifting athletes prepare during the training process, pre-competition processes, during the competition, and during the training process after the competition.

Key words: Weightlifting, skill, physical training, athlete, individual.

The foundation for the training of highly qualified athletes is laid from a young age. In addition to living conditions, genetic characteristics, the ability of each child to exercise, it depends on the introduction of the physical education system into life. However, regardless of the importance of the mentioned aspects, they are not resolved in this case.

Types of training of athletes include physical, technical, psychological and tactical training. V.G. Determining the level of physical preparation of weightlifters for competition, Oleshko averaged the number of special auxiliary control exercises in his research. With the help of a large number of control standards, it is possible to know more precisely the level of physical training of weightlifters. During the pedagogical experience, it was determined that the results of half-squatting hand-ups in athletes of different weight categories and different qualifications were $80 \pm 2.9\%$ in hand-ups, half-squatting and swinging the barbell to the chest $82 \pm 3.3\%$.

A high level of sports results requires the athletes to have a high level of physical fitness, as well as the perfect mastering of reasonable movement techniques. Therefore, the problem of improving technical skills in sports training is urgent.

Technical training is monitored in various ways. It can be the trainer himself and video equipment. Reasonable situations in the last moments of the phases should serve as a goal, but a more accurate assessment of the kinematic and dynamic indicators of the technique can only be realized if a complex method is used.

The pedagogical process of training the personality of a weightlifter is based on the correct individual approach and involves knowing the individual psychological characteristics of the athlete. For this purpose, a psychological description - a psychological card of a person is created.

Recently, a systematic-structural approach has become widespread in the study of sports techniques. A.N. According to Bernstein (1947-1966), movement is not a chain of details, but a whole structure that can be divided into details. The systematic-structural approach can be defined as a methodical task of various sports achievements.

The training process in weightlifting sports involves overcoming serious psychological difficulties (first of all, when lifting the largest weights). The goal of overcoming these difficulties, the main condition of training is to regularly improve the athlete's willpower. Exercises that require the athlete to have a high level of technical training (for example, squats and deadlifts) constitute a separate group of difficulties. While learning such exercises, the athlete faces extremely high mental stress, which manifests itself in the form of fear and panic. Mental effort is a complex activity and is a key factor in being ready to perform. However, it has its limits. When the limit is reached, the mental and motor activity of the athlete decreases. In order to prevent mental states such as tension, it is advisable to widely use a complex of preparation and approach exercises.

The diversity of movement, on the one hand, determines the high requirements for the exact execution of movements, and on the other hand, the importance of forming and developing the appropriate training movement imagination in weightlifters. For this, the ideomotor training method is widely used. Its essence

consists in the purposeful development of the ability of athletes to actively imagine the action (muscle-motor sensations).

Getting ready for a specific competition depends on the instructions, that is, what results the athlete wants to achieve in this competition. The pedagogic task of the coach is that he should form the correct instruction in his student, which includes self-assessment according to his capabilities. To a certain extent, the instruction to prepare for competition is more fully realized in the right proportions of mental strain and stagnation.

Mental stress as a factor of personal mobilization is a necessary condition for competitive activity. Its level is determined by the "height" of the instruction set for the competition. However, for various reasons, mental stress is either too much or not enough. In both cases, it is necessary to make an appropriate adjustment to the level of mental stress at the expense of managing the athlete's mental state. Here, athletes are required to be able to use methods of managing mental states (self-confidence, control of attention, coping, sometimes private forms, etc.). The autogenic method of training helps a lot in this. It is covered in special literature. The second factor necessary for the successful implementation of the formed special instruction is the factor of mental endurance (stability). Mental endurance (stability) is the ability to successfully perform competitive actions in the process of high mental stress. Here, the athlete's ability to manage his mental state is also of leading importance.

References

1. Matkarimov.R.M. Theory and methodology of weightlifting: a textbook for physical education institutions. T.: 2015
2. Dvorkin L. S. Weightlifting: a textbook for universities. Moscow: Soviet sport, 2005. - 600 p.
3. Matkarimov R.M. Weightlifters have many years of training scientific and theoretical foundations of the system: Monograph. T.:2021.